

POWDER METALLURGICAL PRODUCTION OF WHISKER REINFORCED
MAGNESIUM ALLOYS

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Many problems arise in the production of whisker reinforced magnesium matrix composites. One possible technique is based on powder metallurgy. Unlike the production of particle reinforced composites in which relative coarse particle sizes can be mixed mechanically whisker reinforced composites need techniques in which the whiskers are not damaged during mixing and subsequent consolidation. One method is to use mixed size powders which one fine sized component can be used to premix with the whiskers. Difficulties arise in the diffusion anneal to produce a homogeneous matrix alloy. Further problems are encountered in consolidation by deformation and due to pores forming by the Kirkendall effect. The influence of production on whisker damage and properties of the composite is discussed for various whisker materials. In particular the variation of the light alloy powder and the treatment influences markedly the properties of the composites. Selected examples are used to demonstrate the property profile as a function of volume fraction of whiskers. An increase in the E-modulus and decrease in the thermal expansion and improvement in strength properties at elevated temperatures is obtained.